

Vebsayt: <http://2ndsun.uz/index.php/yt>

IDEAS AND TEACHINGS FOR THE CONCEPT OF SPIRITUAL AND MORAL EDUCATION OF THE YOUNGER GENERATION IN UZBEKISTAN

Gulomjonov Odiljon Raximjon ugli¹ Ne'matullayeva Hulkaroy Bahromovna²
Aslanboyeva Gulsanam³

4th-year student of National Ideology, Fundamentals of Spirituality and Legal Education of Andizhan State University, Republic of Uzbekistan¹

1st-year student of Pedagogical Institute of Andijan State University²

Andizhan State University, Faculty of Social Economics, Applied Psychology 2nd stage 201-group³

INFO:

Accepted: 17.03.2022

Reviewed: 17.03.2022

Published: 18.03.2022

Keywords: *Idea, teachings, people, youth, state, independence, culture, law, law*

ABSTRACT

The article reveals the history of development, evolution, and the main features of the education of young people in a period of globalization. The article discusses the idea of educating the younger generation, youth in the works of Eastern thinkers, educational scientists like Abdarauf Fitrat, Abdullah Avlani Jadid of Turkestan, including educational reform at the present stage of Uzbekistan. The author paid attention to the relevance of the study of political and legal doctrines, works of thinkers of the East, which has an important role in educating the younger generation in the spirit of patriotism and high legal culture. The study revealed that the family and the social environment of communication have a great influence on the formation of civil positions in young people. The role of mahallas, educational institutions, and the media is noted. The youth of Uzbekistan is characterized by a high degree of patriotism, which is expressed in love for the Motherland, selfless service and readiness to protect it.

Copyright © 2022. [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/)

The results of the study show that in the system of life values of young people today, one of the main priorities is education. This is expressed in the desire of young Uzbeks to constantly raise the level of education. This is indicated by the overwhelming majority of students in schools, colleges and lyceums, every second young man and girl with a higher education, with secondary and specialized secondary education, university students. general, long-term studies of the dynamics of life values, morality and social attitudes of young people in Uzbekistan show that in the years of independence, young Uzbeks form new priorities in the system of values, interests and social norms. This is an active life position, autonomy, purposefulness, social mobility, which is reflected in their national self-awareness and sustainably positive social well-being.

As we know, the change in the state-political and socio-economic system, not only in our country, but also in all countries of the world, has created a fundamentally new situation in the field of education. A new approach to the educational system and upbringing is being formed in society youth. The state of the current system of education can be assessed as extremely complex, which is associated with the collapse of the main elements of educational policy and values, the search for new guidelines in education and upbringing. Therefore, today one of the most acute and strategically important problems is the problem of education and upbringing of the younger generation in the context of globalization and a rapidly changing world. The problem of education has come to the fore in recent years. Firstly - and this is the main thing, since the whole world is now going through a period of generational change, just as today Uzbekistan is a country of youth. Therefore, one of the most important issues today related to the formation of a new state and society, the implementation of youth policy, which has become an objective necessity - more than 60 percent of the population of Uzbekistan are young people.

The problems of spiritual and moral education are connected with the fact that in the modern world a person lives and develops among many different sources of strong influence on him, both negative and positive (mass media, communications, extraordinary events in various parts of the world, natural disasters, etc.), which constantly fall on the immature intellect and feelings of a young individual, on his emerging sphere of morality. It is becoming increasingly difficult for the younger generation to figure out what is true for them and what is false. Spirituality and morality, as you know, is nothing more than the basis of a personality characteristic, which runs like a red thread through all his activities and behavior, legal relations, and it is not always easy to reveal such a fact. Thirdly, the next urgent task in the field of educational work with young people is the education of a behavioral culture, a culture of everyday life. A person, communicating with people around him, expresses his feelings, emotions, realizes himself in actions. Unfortunately, in modern conditions, the education of a culture of behavior, both at school and in other educational institutions, including universities, is clearly not in the place that is required. Often young people do not know how to control their emotions, do not think about how much their behavior causes discomfort to others, do not know the basic rules of communication. Work on the moral and legal culture of youth requires special attention.

Also, in the Decree of the President of our country "On the Action Strategy for the Further Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan" dated February 7, 2017, a number of tasks for the development of the social sphere, in particular, the sphere of education and science, are defined. The document provides for strengthening the material and technical base of educational institutions, building new ones, reconstructing and overhauling existing ones, equipping them with modern

educational and laboratory equipment, computers and teaching aids. A program for the radical improvement of the higher education system in 2017-2021 will be developed, work will be carried out to further improve curricula, gradually increase the independence of higher education institutions by expanding their powers to use additional sources of funding and provide paid services. Over the past year, about seventy relevant resolutions, decrees and orders of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Cabinet of Ministers have been adopted, which marked the beginning of a new stage in the radical reform of the education system.

In short, the dictionaries of synonyms of the first stage are mainly composed of lists, the vocabulary is organized on the basis of thematic principles, used to teach rhetoric, to understand the subtle semantic differences of words and to use them in speech. It is observed that not only lists, but also their explanations are given, the comments also contain information about the historical development of synonyms, whether they are specific to oral or literary language, whether they are their own or assimilated layer word.¹

The presented article includes national-cultural outlook by zoonym components and the importance are discussed. Zoonyms are used widely to give advice, to show the right way, to give a lesson, to enlighten the philosophy of life, human and nature, human and the universe, human and so on.²

The article presents a comparative analysis of paremias containing the names of food products and expressing the specific characteristics of the Russian and Uzbek linguistic cultures. As a material, Russian and Uzbek paremias are used, containing the names of food products, analysis of proverbs and sayings of the Russian language and their comparison with Uzbek proverbs and sayings allows you to add new details to the gastronomic picture of the world that has developed among the two nations and have been consolidated in the language.³

Since computers started to be introduced in language learning (and in education in general) people have rightly asked whether the investment we are making in these technologies gives us value for money. As digital technologies have taken a hold in society in general, this particular question is not asked quite so often, but it is still important to make sure that the technologies that we have available are used effectively.⁴

The article discusses about studying of a propaedeutic course of the Russian literature in a context of the theory of intercultural communications. In the presented scientific direction, the most perspective are problems of comparative-historical, rather-typological studying different national literatures.⁵

The language portfolio is considered as an instrument of self-realization, self-esteem, self-perfection. An excerpt of a practical lesson in the discipline Russian language with gaming

¹ Mirxanova, G. R. (2022). STAGES OF ENHANCEMENT OF SYNONYM DICTIONARIES. *International Journal of World Languages*, 2(1).

² Tosheva, D. (2016). National-cultural outlook onto the zoonym component aphorisms. *Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities Research*, 4(03), 22-25.

³ Maxmutovna, M. L. (2022). LINGUOCULTURAL FEATURES OF GASTRONOMIC PAREMIAS IN RUSSIAN AND UZBEK LANGUAGES. *Emergent: Journal of Educational Discoveries and Lifelong Learning (EJEDL)*, 3(1), 111-116.

⁴ Bozorova, N. X., & Salixova, Z. A. Using Technology to Assist in Vocabulary Acquisition and Reading Comprehension. *International Journal on Integrated Education*, 2(6), 213-215.

⁵ Sharipovna, B. M. (2020). Studying of a propaedeutic course of the Russian literature in a context of the theory of intercultural communications. *Academy*, 4 (55).

technologies and a table to test the acquired skills of students with a professional orientation based on the results of the lesson are given.⁶

The main criterion for evaluating literary translation is not only close to the original text, but also preserves the style of work and the individual style of the author. In this short article we will try to find out why you need a translator to adequately cope with the solution of the designated contact problem.⁷

People do not understand everything when they are born, but have to learn everything so that they are able to understand. Take learning Foreign language for example; not everyone can understand it, but some non-native speakers can use the language very well. This is not only the case with foreign language, but also other subjects. Therefore, during the learning process, one might find that some people can learn every subject or several subjects very quickly and well. On the other hand, some people have problems learning.⁸

The nature of the semantic volume of the word, language corpus and creating Uzbek language corpus is under the analysis of this article. This issue of principle importance for semasiological research has been interpreted in different ways in linguistics.⁹

A complex approach to personnel training is necessary in the learning process, therefore, in the Russian language classes, we pay great attention to the formation of students' language competence through professional vocabulary and terminology learned by them in the classroom.¹⁰

The Renaissance in Central Asia resulted in the greatest achievements in the political, economic and spiritual life of society. During this period, political and legal sciences, new literature and art, medicine, philosophy, and a new aesthetic consciousness were created.¹¹

As of now, the state policy of women, including women, in Uzbekistan, to protect the legitimate and social interests of women, to ensure full participation of women in the political life of the country, to ensure gender equality and reproductive health, is highly appreciated by the world community, namely, the International Labour Organization, UNICEF, the World Health Organization.¹²

The ongoing reforms paid special attention to the issues of mastering professions by young people, educating students in the spirit of patriotism. At the same time, great importance is attached to the study of the rich heritage of our great ancestors by young people, the education of the younger generation as their worthy successors, mature personalities.¹³ To support the gifted, a specialized school for in-depth study of disciplines in the direction of information and communication technologies named after Muhammad al-Khwarizmi was organized, which was the first step towards the implementation of this particular task. Also, a resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the establishment of a state specialized general boarding school named after Mirzo

⁶ Shodiyeva, D. Y. (2019). LANGUAGE PORTFOLIO-A TOOL FOR SELF-REALIZATION OF PROFESSIONAL-LANGUAGE COMPETENCIES OF A STUDENT. *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (11), 131-135.

⁷ Муродов, Г., & Саидова, Р. (2017). Интерпретация терминов и их анализ. *Молодой ученый*, (13), 703-705.

⁸ TX, A. S. A. Learning Strategies and Learner Characteristics. *International Journal on Integrated Education*, 2(6), 206-208.

⁹ Bahodirovna, A. D. Semantic Labeling of Language Units. *International Journal on Integrated Education*, 3(1), 177-179.

¹⁰ Саидова, М. Р., & Болтаева, М. Ш. (2020). Обучение профессиональным и общекультурным компетенциям студентов направления «туризм» на занятиях русского языка. *Достижения науки и образования*, (5 (59)), 48-50.

¹¹ Tolibjonovich, M. T. (2021). EASTERN RENAISSANCE AND ITS CULTURAL HERITAGE: THE VIEW OF FOREIGN RESEARCHERS. *ResearchJet Journal of Analysis and Inventions*, 2(05), 211-215.

¹² Фуломжонов, О. Р. Ў. (2021). ЖАМИЯТ ТАРАҚҚИЁТИНИНГ ЯНГИ БОСҚИЧИДА ГЕНДЕР ТЕНГЛИКНИ ТАЪМИНЛАШНИНГ ИЖТИМОЙ АҲАМИЯТИ. *Scientific progress*, 1(4).

¹³ Decree of the President of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev "On the Strategy of Actions for the Further Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan" dated February 7, 2017

Ulugbek and a park of astronomy and aeronautics" was adopted. From the 2018/-2019 academic year, gold and silver medals are being established in Uzbekistan for the most successful school graduates. This is provided for by the presidential decree on improving the quality of work on educating young people dated August 14.¹⁴

LIST OF USED LITERATURE:

1. Mirxanova, G. R. (2022). STAGES OF ENHANCEMENT OF SYNONYM DICTIONARIES. *International Journal of World Languages*, 2(1).
2. Tosheva, D. (2016). National-cultural outlook onto the zoonym component aphorisms. *Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities Research*, 4(03), 22-25.
3. Maxmutovna, M. L. (2022). LINGUOCULTURAL FEATURES OF GASTRONOMIC PAREMIAS IN RUSSIAN AND UZBEK LANGUAGES. *Emergent: Journal of Educational Discoveries and Lifelong Learning (EJEDL)*, 3(1), 111-116.
4. Bozorova, N. X., & Salixova, Z. A. Using Technology to Assist in Vocabulary Acquisition and Reading Comprehension. *International Journal on Integrated Education*, 2(6), 213-215.
5. Sharipovna, B. M. (2020). Studying of a propaedeutic course of the Russian literature in a context of the theory of intercultural communications. *Academy*, (4 (55)).
6. Shodiyeva, D. Y. (2019). LANGUAGE PORTFOLIO-A TOOL FOR SELF-REALIZATION OF PROFESSIONAL-LANGUAGE COMPETENCIES OF A STUDENT. *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (11), 131-135.
7. Муродов, Г., & Саидова, Р. (2017). Интерпретация терминов и их анализ. *Молодой ученый*, (13), 703-705.
8. TX, A. S. A. Learning Strategies and Learner Characteristics. *International Journal on Integrated Education*, 2(6), 206-208.
9. Bahodirovna, A. D. Semantic Labeling of Language Units. *International Journal on Integrated Education*, 3(1), 177-179.
10. Саидова, М. Р., & Болтаева, М. Ш. (2020). Обучение профессиональным и общекультурным компетенциям студентов направления «туризм» на занятиях русского языка. *Достижения науки и образования*, (5 (59)), 48-50.
11. Tolibjonovich, M. T. (2021). EASTERN RENAISSANCE AND ITS CULTURAL HERITAGE: THE VIEW OF FOREIGN RESEARCHERS. *ResearchJet Journal of Analysis and Inventions*, 2(05), 211-215.
12. Фуломжонов, О. Р. Ў. (2021). ЖАМИЯТ ТАРАҚҚИЁТИНИНГ ЯНГИ БОСҚИЧИДА ГЕНДЕР ТЕНГЛИКНИ ТАЪМИНЛАШНИНГ ИЖТИМОЙ АҲАМИЯТИ. *Scientific progress*, 1(4).
13. Decree of the President of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev "On the Strategy of Actions for the Further Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan" dated February 7, 2017

¹⁴ Avesta. "The Law Against the Devas" (Videvdat). -adapted translation, research and comments by E.V. Rtveladze, A.Kh. Saidova, E.V. Abdullaeva. - St. Petersburg: Publishing house of the Polytechnic University, 2008.

14. Avesta. "The Law Against the Devas" (Videvdat). -adapted translation, research and comments by E.V. Rtveldze, A.Kh. Saidova, E.V. Abdullaeva. - St. Petersburg: Publishing house of the Polytechnic University, 2008.